

A Study on the Tribe's of Andaman & Nicobar Islands

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Introduction :

Andaman & Nicobar Islands is commonly known as mini India and the capital city of the islands is Port Blair. Andaman and Nicobar Islands is the Union Territory of India. It is located in Indian Ocean, in the southern reach of the Bay of Bengal, near to Indonesia and Thailand. The Tribal's are an intrinsic part of our national life and with their rich cultural heritage. They have been contributing a lot to the complex amalgam. The tribal's settled down in India in pre-historic times, inhabiting mostly in the sparsely populated parts of the forests of North and Middle Andaman, South Andaman, Strait Island, Little Andaman, Great Nicobar, Sentinel Islands in Andaman and Nicobar Islands.

The tribal's are primitive and prefer living in isolation in dense forests or remote areas which is generally cut-off from civilized area. Hence, tribal's have

limited contact with other societies. The habit of isolation helps them to preserve their social customs, traditions and beliefs to a large extent. The territorial distribution of tribes overlaps the political boundaries of the state and territory. They so called “Tribal’s” of India are the indigenous people of the land, in the sense that they have been long settled in different parts of the country before the Aryan speaking people penetrated India to settled down first in Kabul and Indus valleys and then within a millennium and a half, to spread out over large parts of the country along the plains and river valleys.

Concept :

The term “tribe” refers to cultural and historical concept. It is used in terms of the folk urban continuum along which different groups are classified, given a certain order of material culture and a stage of technological growth and classified as tribes.

Background on the Tribals of A & N Islands :**The Andaman Islands are home to four ‘Negrito’ tribes :**

- i. Great Andamanese
- ii. Onge
- iii. Jarawa
- iv. Sentinelese

The ‘Negrito’ tribes are believed to have arrived in the islands from Africa up to 60,000 years ago. All are nomadic hunter-gatherers, hunting wild pig and monitor lizard, and catching fish with bows and arrows. They also collect honey, roots and berries from the forest.

The Nicobar Islands are home to two ‘Mongoloid’ tribes :

- v. The Shompen
- vi. Nicobarese

The 'Mongoloid' tribes probably came to the islands from the Malay- Burma coast several thousand years ago. And their languages are very different to one another.

Some facts about Andaman & Nicobar Islands Tribes :

i. The Great Andamanese :

The Great Andamanese is a collective term used for 6 Nos. different tribes that lived in most of the large islands in the Andaman. These tribes spoke different but related languages were of Negrito origin and were related by culture and geography. Until the late 18th century, the Andamanese peoples were preserved from outside influences by their fierce rejection of contacts (which included killing any shipwrecked foreigners) and by the remoteness of the islands. But after the coming of the British, things changed.

When the British first tried to enter the island in around 1788-89 the Andamanese tribes, with their total population of 5000-8000, were able to resist them, resulting in the British to move to Port Conwallis and withdraw from all attempts to obtain Port Blair and Ross island for about 60 years.

ii. The Onge :

Onges are one of the most primitive tribes in India. They belong to the Negrito racial stock and they have been mainly seen near the Dugong creek in Little Andaman. They are dependent on the food provided by nature and are a semi-nomadic tribe. The onge population fell post british colonization from 672 in 1986 to 92 in 1901, but has remained stable since.

At present the Onge population have opened up to the locals in the island. They have now experienced the impact of outsiders, as efforts at befriending them have proved successful. They have been provided with pucca houses, food, clothes, medicine, etc. by the Administration. They eat turtle, fish, roots and jack fruits, etc. They have developed artistry and crafts. The Onges can make canoes. A primary school has also been functioning at the Dugong Creek settlement of Onges. The population of this tribe is stable and is at present 110.

iii. The Jarawa :

With a population between 250 to 400, the Jarawa tribe is one of the largest tribes in the Andaman Islands. For centuries this tribe has shunned all interaction with outsiders and therefore their name means “The hostile ones” or “people of the earth”.

The Jarawa are still at the primitive stage of life on earth. They entirely depend upon forest and sea for food. Wild boar and monitor lizard are consumed. Various kinds of fruit, honey, and tubers are parts of their diet too. The Jarwas of both sexes goes completely naked. However, some ornaments made with shells and palm leaves are worn by them but these are not in the sense to cover their nudity.

iv. The Sentinelese :

The Sentinelese people are said to be so hostile that their home has been named the ‘hardest place to visit in the world. They inhabit the North Sentinel island and are the only remaining tribe in the Andamans to still maintain their isolation from the rest of the world. Nobody knows exactly how they look, the population, or how they live. Since 1967, the Indian governments with the help of anthropologists have tried to make contact with the tribe. They tried giving gifts of food, coconuts, etc. but they were always met with hostility. The tribe showers arrows and stones at whoever comes near the island.

v. The Shompen :

The Shompens are Mongoloids and inhabit the Great Nicobar Island, are a semi-nomadic tribe that was first discovered by Steen Bille a Danish admirer in 1846. The total population of Shompens is estimated to be 214 whereas during 1901 Census the population recorded was 348 approximately. They are of medium height with Mongoloid features. They were believed to be hostile earlier but in recent decades they have not shown any hostility and now have established trade relations with Nicobarese. The main activities of Shompens are hunting, food-gathering (They collect wild yams, roots, fruit, honey and insect larvae) and fishing. They love to hunt pig with their spears and they take help of pet dogs while hunting.

They are nomads and wander from place to place within the jungles. They live in self-made huts. They are shy in nature and avoid to interact with others. Administration provides them free food, utensils, drinking water and medical facilities. A school is present near their area to impart formal as well as non-formal education. The Shompen, who according to 1991 census, are only 131 in number, are found to reside in the Great Nicobar Island which has an area of 865 Sq km. The island is hilly in terrain with full of vegetation. According to Man (1886) the Shompen are the original inhabitants of the Great Nicobar but later on they were pushed to the interior part of the island.

vi. Nicobarese :

The Nicobarese have Mongloid features and they are a large population of over 27,000 (2001 census). They are horticulturist and pig-herders inhabiting large permanent villages mostly close to sea shore. They are not divisible into tribes, but there are territorial distinctions. Thus they may be fairly divided into five groups such as The people of Car Nicobar, Chowra, Teressa with Bompoka, The Central Group, and The Southern Group but differences to be observed is language, customs, manners and physiognomy of the several groups may, with some confidence, be referred to habitat and the physical difficulties of communication. Nicobari Families are patriarchal and as a rule live jointly. This joint family is known as Tuhēt. There is no individual ownership, but the Tuhēt owns land, coconut and pigs. Love marriage is very common and the age of marriage is sufficiently high. The chief article of food is the coconut, next in importance been Pandanus pulp, fish and rice.

Conclusion :

The Tribal's people of the Andaman and Nicobar islands are neither 'primitive' nor living in the 'stone age'. Their way of life has not remained unchanged for thousands of years. Like all peoples, their cultures have been continuously evolving. There is no reason why the tribes cannot both survive and thrive, as long as their lands and resources are secure.

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